

Electrical and colloidal properties of hydrogenated nanodiamonds: effects of structure, composition and size

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Highlights

- Colloidal stability and hydration of H-NDs are enhanced by defects.
- Electrical conductivity of H-NDs is controlled by crystal quality and diminishes below 3 nm.
- At least, two mechanisms participate in the electrical conductivity of H-ND.
- Infrared transmission at 1330 cm⁻¹ correlates with electrical conductivity of H-NDs.

Keywords: Nanodiamond, Hydrogenation, Positive zeta potential, Conductivity, FTIR

Abstract

Hydrogenated nanodiamonds (NDs) get increasing attention as promising nanomaterial in biology as well as optoelectronics. This study shows how the ND synthesis process and ND size are reflected in their different colloidal/hydration and electronic properties. We employ three different ND types: detonation ND (DND), top-down high-pressure high-temperature ND (TD_HPHT ND) prepared by milling of HPHT monocrystals, and bottom-up high-pressure high-temperature ND (BU_HPHT ND) prepared by HPHT synthesis from chloroadamantane. Zeta potential measurements and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analysis (FTIR) reveal the best colloidal stability in neutral to basic pH and the strongest affinity to water for DND. Electrical and FTIR measurements connected with an annealing treatment show a steep increase of electrical conductivity in BU_HPHT ND above 2 nm and reveal different contribution of transfer doping in BU_HPHT ND and TD_HPHT ND despite similar conductivity values ($\approx 10^{-5}$ S.cm⁻¹). We also confirm the correlation of the ND conductivity with IR transmission at the phonon frequency of the diamond (1330 cm⁻¹). Neutron irradiation of a TD_HPHT

ND corroborates the crucial role of structural defects in the above colloidal and electronic properties of hydrogenated nanodiamonds.

Introduction

Fascinating properties of hydrogen-terminated bulk diamond such as surface conductivity and negative electron affinity have been the subject of intense research in the past decades. Comprehensive information is provided in the recent review of Crawford et al.[1]. These unique electronic properties together with outstanding mechanical properties, biocompatibility, chemical stability, and large-scale production availability in various forms and shapes make the hydrogen-terminated diamond favorable for multiple applications from field-effect transistors to bio-sensing and emission of solvated electrons for hardly reductive species such as N_2 [2] or CO_2 [3].

Nanoparticles of diamond, nowadays well known as nanodiamonds (ND), bring these outstanding diamond properties to the nanoscale and offer a much higher surface-to-volume ratio than bulk diamond forms. However, due to the great variety in ND synthesis and processing, the actual properties can differ substantially. ND were first identified in soot from detonated explosives[4]. These detonation nanodiamonds (DND) raised particular interest due to their inherently narrow size distribution with a mean size of around 5 nm. However, due to the highly non-equilibrium detonation process, the DND composition and microstructure are rather complex, affecting DND optical and electronic properties[5,6]. Interstitial and substitutional nitrogen atoms, vacancies, dangling bonds, isolated sp^2 -C defects, and high content of inner and surface non-diamond carbon are all typical features of DND[7–10]. Motivated by a high scientific interest and application demands, other sources of nanodiamonds were explored. The most notable ones are nanodiamonds made by milling of high-pressure high-temperature (HPHT) microdiamonds that are well-established industrial product. These NDs, further abbreviated as the top-down HPHT ND (TD_HPHT ND), have irregular shapes and monocrystalline structure which distinguishes them from DND[11] and makes them suitable for hosting stable color centers such as nitrogen-vacancy center with outstanding photoluminescent and sensing properties[12–14]. A novel class of HPHT ND prepared by bottom-up HPHT synthesis (BU_HPHT ND) from halogenated adamantanes in the tens of mg amount in one run was reported recently[15–17]. The BU_HPHT ND can be considered as the best of both worlds compared to TD_HPHT ND and DND owing to the monocrystalline structure, excellent sp^3 -C phase purity, the precise size control in the range of 1-8 nm, and complete surface hydrogenation formed during the synthesis[18]. This distinguishes them from both DND and TD_HPHT NDs since these must be hydrogenated by a post-treatment such as exposure to hydrogen plasma. This approach is commonly used to create hydrogen termination of diamond monocrystals and thin films[19] and is also applicable to ND[20–22]. However, a simpler and more convenient process is annealing in the hydrogen gas. This process has been introduced by Ando et al.[23] who proposed a radical nature of the reaction; the radicals being formed during the surface functional group desorption from the ND surface. The radical mechanism was later confirmed by Ahmed et al.[24] who identified that the C3 radicals evolve and attack the hydrogen molecules which then react with the ND surface dangling bonds forming the surface C-H_x bonds. It has been shown several times that while the comparably smaller and defective DND reacts with hydrogen at a relatively low temperature (500-600°C)[25,26] a higher temperature of 750°C - 800°C is needed to fully hydrogenate the sub-50 nm HPHT ND[27–29].

Hydrogenation provides ND with several interesting properties that do not find its analogy in the hydrogen-terminated bulk diamond. While some electronic properties of hydrogenated ND such as work function were shown to be similar to hydrogenated bulk diamond[30], the reported conductivity values on hydrogenated DND[26,31] does not reach the values of the hydrogenated bulk diamond. Another unique difference is the interaction of ND with water. Hydrogenated bulk diamond surface is considered hydrophobic having a high contact angle[32] but hydrogenated DND are rather hydrophilic. This is connected with, perhaps the most peculiar property of the hydrogenated ND, strongly positive

zeta potential and high isoelectric point (IEP)[25]. This unique feature has been used and proposed in multiple applications including virus removal from water[33], drug and protein delivery[34], and cell-signaling protein regulation via outstandingly strong affinity to FGF2 molecules[28,35] etc. The origin of the highly positive zeta potential remains a matter of active research. It has been proposed that the positive zeta potential arises due to the protonation of the surface sp^2 -C structures characteristic for ND[36]. However, it remains unclear how and why the protonation of the otherwise hydrophobic C- H_x carbon surface occurs. Petit et al.[37] showed that the water hydrogen bonds are heavily disturbed due to a strong localization of charge at or near the hydrogenated DND surface which provides an image of a highly negatively charged sp^2 -C surface that readily protonates and it is thus detected as the positive zeta potential.

The recent achievements in the preparation of hydrogenated ND other than DND provides a unique opportunity to elucidate the effect of the ND crystal quality, ND surface structure, and ND size on the electrical conductivity and colloidal properties including surface hydration. In this work, we thus investigate these properties and their mutual relations by Raman and infrared spectroscopies, and electrical conductivity and zeta potential measurements.

Experimental

Materials

Three ND types were employed in this study. DND were purchased from New Metals and Chemicals Corp., Japan (purity > 98%). The mean size of the primary DND particles is ~ 5 nm. As TD_HPHT ND we used Monocrystalline Synthetic ND (Pureon, Switzerland) with a mean size of 18, 50 and 125 nm. BU_HPHT ND were synthesized from 1-chloroadamantane as already described earlier[18,38,39]. By variation of the synthesis time and pressure, the size of the ND can be finely tuned. Here, the ND size range spanned from 1.2 nm to 8 nm. The detailed size, structure, and surface chemistry characterization can be found elsewhere[18,38–40].

Hydrogenation of NDs and preparation of colloidal solutions

As received DND and TD_HPHT ND powders were first oxidized at 450°C for 30 min (DND) and 300 min (TD_HPHT ND) and then hydrogenated by annealing in hydrogen gas for 6 h at atmospheric pressure at 700 °C for DND and 800-1000 °C for TD_HPHT ND. The details as well as the surface chemistry changes documented by FTIR can be found in the previous works [28,29,41,42]. Since the TD_HPHT ND contain a non-negligible amount of non-diamond carbon on the surface, they were purified by annealing in air at 450°C for 5 h prior the hydrogenation. The DND were hydrogenated as received. DNDs contain some non-diamond carbon on the surface which, however, cannot be completely removed, it is also largely present inside the particles [7]. The treatment we use for DND (450°C, 30 min) has been proven to work for surface oxidation and a certain purification effect [6]. However, more harsh conditions only lead to the burning of the DND particles while their overall defective structure remains [43]. The BU_HPHT ND are fully hydrogenated after the synthesis and thus they were used as received and did not undergo any thermal treatment. Colloidal solutions were prepared by dispersing the ND powder in demineralized water using a rod-type sonicator (Hielscher, UP200s) at 200 W for 1 h under water cooling.

Size and zeta potential measurements

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) apparatus (Zetasizer Nano ZS, Malvern Panalytical, UK) equipped with a helium–neon laser (633 nm) and the scattering angle of 173° was used for the measurement. The refractive index of bulk diamond (2.4) and the viscosity of pure water (0.89004 mPa.s at 25°C) were

used. Every sample was measured three times, and each of the three DLS size measurement consisted of 10 runs lasting 10 s. In the graphs, we provide the Z-average value, a characteristic value of size, obtained as the intensity weighted mean hydrodynamic size. A mean zeta potential value was calculated automatically in the software from Henry equation after estimation of the electrophoretic mobilities of the particles under the applied voltage in the zeta potential measurement cell. The zeta potential value was calculated as the average from 3 zeta potential values. Both measurements were done in a disposable zeta potential measurement cell. Z-average and zeta potential values as a function of pH were obtained manually to ensure ND equilibration with the base. Eppendorf-type tubes in 2 ml volume, were filled by 1 ml of dispersed ND and aliquots of 0.25M NaOH were added. The size and zeta potential of such prepared ND suspensions were measured after 5 h, photos of the suspensions were taken after 1 week.

Spectroscopic characterization

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was measured by Thermo Nicolet iS50 spectrometer equipped with the KBr beam splitter and N₂-cooled MCT detector. The measurement chamber was continuously purged with dried air, ensuring very low water vapor pressure. All spectra were measured by a specular-apertured grazing angle reflectance (SAGA) method with an 80° incident light. Each spectrum represents an average of 128 scans per spectrum collected in the range of 4000–1000 cm⁻¹ at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution. 50 µL of the ND colloidal solution was dropcasted on Au-coated Si substrates and briefly heated at 100 °C for 60 s to evaporate the liquid. Such obtained spectra are labeled “as deposited”. A bare Au substrate was measured as a background prior to each sample measurement. Then, the samples were annealed at 250°C for one hour at ambient conditions on a hot plate, placed into the measurement chamber and measured immediately. Such obtained spectra are labeled “250°C/1h”. These conditions were adopted from our previous work where only annealing at 250°C was able to significantly reduce the surface water on DNDs [30]. Then the samples were left at ambient conditions at a relative humidity 50-60% for 24 hours and measured again. Such obtained spectra are labeled “24h ambient”.

Raman spectra were obtained by a Renishaw InVia system equipped with a 442 nm excitation laser. The samples were deposited from the ND colloidal solutions on Si substrates by dropcasting and drying. The laser power was kept below 1 mW. The accumulation time was 5 × 100 s.

Electrical conductivity measurement

The ND electrical conductivity was measured on an interdigitated electrodes (IDE) sensor (Micrux, Spain). The circular sensing part of the IDE structure (diameter 3.5 mm) consisted of 180 pairs of Au electrodes on glass (5 µm width, 5 µm gap between the electrodes, electrode thickness of 200 nm (150 nm Au and 50 nm Ti as adhesive layer)). This structure showed excellent adhesion of the ND samples and stability during resistivity measurements. Before the ND deposition, the IDE electrodes were stepwise cleaned in acetone, isopropyl alcohol and deionized water in an ultrasonic bath for 10 minutes in each liquid and dried by nitrogen flow. The NDs were deposited from their colloidal solutions (1 mg/ml) by dropcasting of 25 µl of the ND solution using a micropipette. The deposit was left dry at ambient conditions for 24 h. Resistance was measured at room temperature using an Agilent 34410A multimeter with a measuring range of up to 1 GΩ.

Neutron irradiation

For neutron irradiation we used the TD_HPHT ND 50, with a mean size of 50 nm in as received state (TD_HPTH ND 50-ar). 32 mg of dry TD_HPHT ND 50 powder sample was placed in a clean quartz ampoule of 0.4 mm internal diameter and flame sealed. Such prepared target was then irradiated in a

research nuclear reactor (LVR-15, CV Řež, Czech Republic)[44] operated at an average thermal power of 9.69 MW in the H6 irradiation channel at position 3 for 9.28 days. Approximate average total neutron flux density at the H6-3 position was $9,5 \times 10^{13}$ n/cm²s. After one-week of cooling period, the ampoule was opened and the NDs powder was recovered for further processing and analyses. A small amount of ¹⁸²Ta produced by the ¹⁸¹Ta(n,γ)¹⁸²Ta neutron capture reaction was identified by the gamma spectrometric analysis (HPGe detector, Ortec, USA) of the NDs sample after irradiation as the only metallic impurity present, presumably originating from the remaining traces of the ND growth catalyst or milling media. The relict trace content of Ta in nanodiamonds was then estimated to be approximately 0.08 % by weight.

Results and discussion

ND structure

The structural differences between the three types of studied ND are clearly revealed by Raman spectroscopy. **Figure 1** shows Raman spectra of DND (blue), TD_HPHT ND 18 nm (red), and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm (orange). The highly defective DND structure provides a characteristic DND Raman spectrum with a broad and shifted Raman diamond peak accompanied by the G band originating from defects and the non-diamond carbon[11,45]. It is important to mention, that the Raman diamond peak red shift and broadening is due to the overall defective and “polycrystalline” structure of DND rather than due to the size of the primary ND particles (≈ 5 nm)[11]. Monocrystalline TD_HPHT ND 18 nm already contains much less of the non-diamond carbon found exclusively only on the ND surface. In the TD_HPHT ND the sp²-C content can be significantly suppressed by multiple oxidation techniques[46–48] but as shown recently, subsequent hydrogenation still leads to a noticeable increase of the surface sp²-C content[28,29]. This is possibly caused by an inherent surface rearrangement due to the surface functional groups desorption and radical release during the “*ex-situ*” hydrogenation process[24]. In contrast to the DND and TD_HPHT ND 18 nm spectra, the Raman spectrum of a representative BU_HPHT ND 8 nm is essentially sp²-C free demonstrating excellent diamond phase purity of this ND type. The differences in microstructure and purity are corroborated also by the TEM images shown next to the spectra. Note also the absence of the brownish hue of the colloid compared to the other two ND types as shown by the cuvette photographs. It qualitatively confirms the excellent diamond phase purity. This is a result of the HPHT synthesis route and near-thermodynamic equilibrium conditions that lead to well-developed and faceted diamond nanocrystals with a fully hydrogenated surface[39,40]. The bending modes of surface C-H_x groups in BU_HPHT ND 8 nm spectrum are found at 1250, 1340 and 1460 cm⁻¹, highlighted by the dotted lines. The features at 1150 and 1450 cm⁻¹ are similar to those regularly observed in the CVD-grown polycrystalline diamond films and have been assigned to trans-polyacetylene (TPA) located at the intergrain boundaries, i.e., at the “inner surface” of the diamond crystallites in a polycrystalline diamond film. The 1340 cm⁻¹ feature was explained by its coupling with the ~ 1330 cm⁻¹ diamond phonons[49]. The above analysis thus highlights very different inner as well as surface structure of the three ND types in terms of the crystal quality and the non-diamond carbon content.

Figure 1. Raman spectra, TEM images and photographs of colloidal solutions (1 mg/ml) of DND (blue), TD_HPHT ND 18 nm (red), and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm (orange). (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

ND electrical conductivity

The electrical conductivity of the studied ND samples as a function of ND size, structure (type) and for TD_HPHT ND also of hydrogenation temperature is plotted in the **Figure 2a**. The outstanding ND size control of the bottom up synthesis from the halogenated adamantanes[15,38,39] allowed us to obtain size-resolved data in the sub-10 nm region, i.e. in the region characteristic of a tremendous change of surface to volume ratio. The data shows that in the sub-2 nm region, the conductivity is very low ($\approx 10^{-11}$ S/cm) but steeply increases over six orders of magnitude ($\approx 10^{-5}$ S/cm) as soon as the ND size exceeds 2 nm and reaches a plateau for 4.6 nm ND and larger. This abrupt conductivity evolution correlates with already identified morphological and spectral changes of BU_HPHT ND that occur at around 2 nm[18]. TEM has shown that the sub-2 nm BU_HPHT ND lack the nanoparticle character in the sense of well-developed nanocrystals and their structure and atomic arrangement are not fully understood at the moment[50]. As soon as the size of BU_HPHT ND exceeds 2-3 nm, the diamond nanoparticles start to appear and well-developed, faceted nanocrystals are observed from 4.6 nm onward. This morphological transition has been recently documented also spectroscopically by evolution of the C-H_x stretches from broad bands to sharp peaks in FTIR spectra, indicating an atomically-ordered surface[18].

Interestingly, the TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and 50 nm samples have similar conductivity as the BU_HPHT ND 3.4 - 8 nm samples. The conductivity of TD_HPHT ND 125 nm is already noticeably lower. To demonstrate the crucial effect of hydrogenation, we also measured the conductivity of the initial, oxidized TD_HPH ND (18 nm, 50 nm and 125 nm) before hydrogenation. These data are plotted in the supporting information (Figure S1) showing about five orders of magnitude difference between the oxidized and hydrogenated surfaces of TD_HPH ND. Please note, that the conductivity of oxidized DND was out of the range of the used equipment, i.e. lower than 10^{-12} S.cm⁻¹. Due to increasing TD_HPHT ND size from 18 to 125 nm and expected decreasing reactivity towards molecular hydrogen we tested hydrogenation temperature range 800 – 1000 °C. While for the smallest TD_HPHT ND 18 nm, 800 °C seems to be optimal as the higher temperature leads to oscillation of the conductivity possibly due to

a pronounced formation of the surface non-diamond carbon, both TD_HPHT ND 50 and 125 nm samples require at least 900 °C hydrogenation temperature to reach the highest conductivity. In contrast to TD_HPHT ND 18 nm, the temperatures of 900 - 1000 °C do not yet result in a pronounced formation of the non-diamond carbon in the TD_HPHT ND 50 and 125 nm samples due to their lower reactivity as detected by Raman spectroscopy (see Figure S2 in the supporting information). This also means that excessive formation of the non-diamond surface carbon does not increase the conductivity, i.e., the origin of the conductivity is not related to a surface non-diamond phase and depends on the diamond phase. Rather striking is comparatively low conductivity of DNDs ($\approx 10^{-10}$ S/cm), being close to the value of 2 nm BU_HPHT NDs but far from the values obtained for the BU_HPHT ND 4.6 and 8 nm samples and all TD_HPHT ND samples. This clearly demonstrates the need for high crystal quality to achieve good electrical conductivity in hydrogenated NDs.

Figure 2. ND conductivity as a function of ND size, structure/origin and, for TD_HPHT ND, hydrogenation temperatures (a). Time dependence of the conductivity of the DND, TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm after 1h annealing at 250°C (b). (A color version of this figure can be viewed online.)

In order to better understand conductivity mechanism(s) of hydrogenated ND, we recorded the time-dependence of conductivity of DND, TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm samples immediately after annealing in air at 250 °C for 1 h (Figure 2b). The annealing was done to verify whether the conductivity arises from the transfer-doping effect as in the hydrogenated bulk diamond. In DND, the conductivity first decreases one order of magnitude down to 6.2×10^{-13} S.cm⁻¹ as soon as the sample is transferred from the hot plate to the sample holder of the conductivity measurement setup. used by a too short equilibration time and/or partial oxidation of the C-H_x bonds after the annealing treatment, as confirmed by FTIR further below.

Both BU_HPHT ND 8 nm and TD_HPHT ND 18 nm samples showed an immediate increase in conductivity after the annealing treatment. BU_HPHT ND 8 nm sample showed a relatively weak response; its conductivity remained very high even after the annealing (1.7×10^{-6} S.cm⁻¹) and, within a few hours, recovered to its original value (8.7×10^{-6} S.cm⁻¹). TD_HPHT ND 18 nm sample was more sensitive. Considering the value of 2.5×10^{-8} S.cm⁻¹ achieved immediately after the annealing and the original value of 8.5×10^{-6} S.cm⁻¹, 340-times conductivity decay is observed after the annealing. Even after 22 h, the conductivity remains about 4-times lower than the original value. Thus, in all the ND samples a transfer doping related to surface water is observed; however, its degree and kinetics are strongly influenced by the ND type, i.e., internal and surface structure and chemistry.

ND surface chemistry and free charge carriers

It has been shown recently, that the appearance of a sharp infrared transmission peak at the phonon frequency of diamond 1330 cm^{-1} in FTIR spectra of hydrogenated NDs provides a direct proof of the free charge carriers[51]. The origin of the feature has been assigned to Fano-type destructive interference between zone-center optical phonons and free carriers in the near-surface layer of hydrogenated nanodiamond[51]. Size dependence study has shown that this feature disappears in BU_HPHT NDs smaller than 2 nm[18] which perfectly correlates with the conductivity dependence plotted in Figure 2a. This confirms that this spectral feature is indeed directly linked with the ND conductivity.

To obtain deeper information about the possible conductivity mechanism, the FTIR spectra of the three representative ND samples (DND; blue, TD_HPHT ND 18 nm; red, BU_HPHT ND 8 nm; orange) are shown in **Figure 3** at different state of hydration. We focus first on the 1330 cm^{-1} feature related to the ND conductivity. The upper panel in Figure 3 corresponds to as deposited samples after only a short heating (1 min, 100°C) to evaporate the bulk water. After such a short annealing, more strongly bound surface water is still present. The middle panel shows the spectra recorded after 1 hour annealing at 250°C under ambient conditions. After such an annealing the water content is greatly (but possibly not entirely) reduced[30]. Finally, the lower panel shows the spectra after 1-day equilibration with the ambient conditions after the annealing (250°C , 1h), i.e. rehydration due to ambient humidity occurs.

The 1330 cm^{-1} transmission peak is present in the spectra of as deposited TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm samples (Figure 3; upper panel). In contrast, the DND spectrum exhibits DND-characteristic[20,52] absorption peak at 1330 cm^{-1} . This indicates the absence of free carriers which is consistent with their low conductivity (Figure 2). The appearance of this peak in diamond has been associated with the embedded nitrogen[53], thus, it is not surprising to detect the peak in nitrogen-rich DND. After 1 hour of annealing at 250°C ($250^\circ\text{C}/1\text{ h}$; middle panel), the transmission peak is preserved only in the BU_HPHT ND 8 nm which is consistent with recently published results where the transmission peak completely disappears only above 350°C and is recovered at ambient temperature[40]. The 1 hour annealing at 250°C results only in a 5-times decrease in the conductivity and preservation of the 1330 cm^{-1} transmission peak. In TD_HPHT ND 18 nm, the feature is no longer apparent after the annealing, and it is associated with two orders of magnitude decrease in the conductivity as described above. TD_HPHT ND 18 nm is thus obviously more sensitive to the annealing than the BU_HPHT ND 8 nm. In both TD_HPHT ND and BU_HPHT ND the recovery of the 1330 cm^{-1} transmission feature is observed after the sample is left for 24 hour at ambient conditions (Figure 3, the lower panel).

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of DND (blue), representative TD_HPHT ND 18 nm (red) and representative BU_HPHT ND 8 nm (orange) as deposited (as dep.; upper panel), after 1 hour annealing at 250°C (250°C/1h, middle panel) and after recovery for 24 hour at ambient conditions (24h ambient, lower panel). (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

ND interaction with water

The FTIR spectra in Figure 3 enable us to obtain also valuable information about NDs hydration which is highly dependent on the ND temperature and/or humidity[54]. Interaction of the ND surface with water predetermines its colloidal properties such as sign and magnitude of zeta potential and subsequently formation of (un)stable colloidal solution by formation of an electrical double layer around the NDs. Typically observed strongly positive zeta potential for hydrogenated DNDs is an unusual phenomenon as no other carbon material exhibit this behavior. The affinity of NDs to water

can be readily assessed from the regions of bending and stretching vibrations of OH bonds originating from the adsorbed water. The FTIR spectra of as deposited NDs (upper panel) reveal remarkable differences among the three ND samples. Hydrogenated DNDs show a typical strong affinity to water, manifested by presence of surface bound water (1570 cm^{-1}) along with the bulk water (1620 cm^{-1}) in the OH bending region[30,37] as well as the distinct signal in the OH stretching region. Due to the strong polarity of water molecules, the presence of the bound water component indicates charge accumulation at the hydrogenated DND surface[36] or at hydrogenated DND-water interface, leading to long-range disruption of the water hydrogen bond network manifested by a red-shift of the OH bending mode[30,37]. Critically, this feature could also appear due to a formation of hydrogen bonds between oxygenated surface moieties, giving rise to the signal at 1570 cm^{-1} , and adsorbed water molecules. Such hypothetical oxygenated surface moieties should manifest themselves by a detectable oxygen content that could be quantitatively analyzed by, for example, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). In a previous study, the total oxygen content of the DND hydrogenated at 700°C was found below 2 at.% by XPS[26]. In accordance, a more recent XPS analysis[28] of the here-relevant hydrogenated DND and TD_HPHT ND 18 nm samples confirmed very low oxygen content ($\approx 1\text{ at.}\%$) for both ND types. Still, the 1570 cm^{-1} component appears intense only in the FTIR spectrum of the DND which doubts the assignment to any oxygenated surface moieties otherwise it should appear similarly strong also in the spectrum of the TD_HPHT ND which does not occur. Our results are in line with the recent investigation of larger hydrogenated TD_HPHT NDs where the component at 1570 cm^{-1} was completely absent in the IR spectra of acquired at relative humidity ca. 10% [55].

Another IR feature, specific to DND, is the sharp peak at 3690 cm^{-1} corresponding to the “free” OH bond of water molecules, which typically occurs at hydrophobic interfaces[56]. Appearance of this feature is in peculiar contradiction to the easy formation of stable DND colloids in water. Unlike DND, both TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm show only hints of the surface and bulk OH bending components which indicates important role of the structural defects in the emergence of the 1570 cm^{-1} feature as discussed further below. In addition, the OH broad stretching region is present only in the spectrum of TD_HPHT ND 18 nm.

The FTIR spectra of NDs annealed at 250°C for one hour are shown in the Figure 3, middle panel labeled “ $250^\circ\text{C}/1\text{h}$ ”. The temperature of 250°C was chosen from our previous work[30] where only annealing at 250°C was able to significantly reduce the surface water on DNDs. After the annealing, the OH stretching remains similar in the DND spectrum but the volume water-related 1620 cm^{-1} component is significantly suppressed and the tightly bound surface water gives a clear peak at 1570 cm^{-1} in the bending region in accordance to the previous studies[30,37]. BU_HPHT ND 8 nm shows negligible change in both regions. The only change in the TD_HPHT ND 18 nm is the suppression of the OH stretches after the annealing. Notably, the C=O peak arises at 1700 cm^{-1} in the DND and TD_HPHT ND 18 nm spectra, indicating a certain degree of oxidation after this treatment. No oxidation occurs in BU_HPHT ND 8 nm.

After the annealing NDs were left for 24 hours at ambient conditions and measured (Figure 3, lower panel labeled “24h ambient”). The spectra indicate partial recovery of a rich hydration shell around the DND but not for the other two HPHT NDs.

In conclusion, the FTIR spectra show clear differences between the three types of NDs. In particular, we observed a clear correlation of the 1330 cm^{-1} feature with the ND electrical conductivity, as well as differences in hydration properties, which are manifested by a clear evolution of the surface OH components of water after dehydration and rehydration. DNDs have a very firmly bound hydration layer and overall high affinity to water, while both TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm show weak to negligible affinity to water and nearly no bound water layer.

Figure 4 shows the zeta potential and Z-average particle size as a function of pH for the DND, TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm samples. Zeta potential values of the as prepared solutions which all have pH around 5.5 already show differences in studied samples. The highest zeta potential was for DND (53 mV), followed by TD_HPHT ND 18 nm (45 mV) and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm (30 mV). It is important to emphasize that the zeta potential as function of pH and IEP values are typically obtained by an automatic titration unit connected with a DLS/zeta potential analyzer. However, we noticed that equilibration after each pH change is barely achieved in such a case. Therefore, the data points shown in Figure 4 were recorded manually after 1-hour equilibration with the added base (NaOH) aliquots. The photographs above each graph show the real samples 1 week after the measurements so they do not directly relate to the values plotted in the graphs. It is obvious that the zeta potential of all samples is very sensitive to pH and is significantly reduced already after the first pH increase. Quite surprisingly, the zeta potential of DND remain around 20 mV or more even at high pH of 11 or 12, but the size data as well as the photographs, clearly show aggregation of the DND. The highest pH value at which the DND remain stable after 1 week is 9.

The TD_HPHT ND 18 nm show increase of the Z-average as well as a significant drop in the zeta potential already at pH = 7, which gradually continues, and the complete aggregation occurs around pH = 9. After one week the highest pH in which the TD_HPHT ND 18 nm remains without aggregation is only 5.6. The photograph shows that the boundary is not sharp, and some fractions remain stable till pH = 9.4. At higher pH, all the particles aggregate. Also note that from pH 7 to pH 9, the size of the DND and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm are relatively constant, but the size of TD_HPHT ND 18 nm increases with the increasing pH. We assume that this is due to the broad span of particle size (0-30 nm) and high non-uniformity in their shape compared to the DND and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm samples. We may speculate that the different crystal planes could have varying abilities to acquire and accumulate the surface charge (zeta potential) which could result in gradual aggregation of the surfaces with the lowest charge. In the BU_HPHT ND 8 nm sample, the employed sonication protocol does not lead to complete dispersion of the individual 8 nm NDs, and a Z-average size of around 300 nm is obtained. It is unclear whether it is due to the very strong interparticle bonds or due to the poor dispersibility in water. The size dependence on pH is somewhat similar to the TD_HPHT ND 18 nm sample, i.e., the Z-average size value gradually increases and complete aggregation occurs at pH higher than 9. After one week the highest pH value at which the BU_HPHT ND 8 nm sample remain stable is only 5.5 and similarly to TD_HPHT ND 18 nm some fraction remains stable up to pH = 9.1. At higher pH, all the particles aggregate. The results show that the DND with a specific defective structure exhibits the most robust colloidal properties, providing a solid affinity for water and poor electrical conductivity.

Figure 4. Zeta potential and DLS Z-average size as a function of pH for the DND (a), TD_HPHT ND 18 nm (b) and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm (c) samples. The photographs above show the appearance of the

colloidal samples at indicated pH values that were rested for 1 week after the DLS measurement. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

Impact of defects on the colloidal and electronic properties of hydrogenated NDs

To evaluate and verify the role of structural defects on the electrical and colloidal properties of the hydrogenated NDs we performed neutron irradiation of the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar sample with the aim to approximate its structure to DND. We used the TD_HPHT ND 50 nm sample as a representative of the sub-100 nm TD_HPHT ND type since it covers the size range 0-100 nm. Moreover, we show the differences in the colloidal and electronic properties of the samples 18 nm (size range 0-30 nm) and 50 nm (size range 0-100 nm) are only minor as demonstrated by the close values of conductivity (Figure 2a) and close values of zeta potential at the initial pH (Figure 4b and 5c). Yet, we acknowledge that when using much larger TD_HPHT NDs, the results obtained may not be fully comparable to still significantly smaller DNDs. The results presented in the following section should therefore be seen as comparable to DND in terms of structure rather than size. The effect of the irradiation on the TD_HPHT ND 50 structure was immediately manifested by the appearance of characteristic features of neutron-irradiated diamond in the Raman spectra[57]. Comparison of the starting, non-irradiated TD_HPHT ND 50-ar (red), the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar sample after irradiation (TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr; dark blue), TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr after hydrogenation (TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H; green) and referential hydrogenated TD_HPHT ND 50 (dark yellow) is shown in **Figure 5a**. The non-irradiated TD_HPHT ND 50-ar sample exhibits only a clear and sharp diamond Raman peak at 1331 cm^{-1} , other forms of carbon are negligible. After the irradiation, the Raman spectrum of TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr contains many other features and to some extent resembles the vibrational density of states (VDOS) due to a great reduction of the coherence length. It is due to the loss of the translational symmetry that characterizes the crystalline structure and transition to an amorphous structure. This leads to the localized optical vibrations instead of extended in the whole lattice[45]. In particular, the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr sample spectrum contains broad features in the $250 - 650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the $1000 - 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range and is notably like the spectrum of DNDs. In addition, the broadened diamond peak has a maximum at 1323 cm^{-1} which is also close to a value often reported for DNDs[45]. Finally, the peak arising at 1620 cm^{-1} is also typical for the deeply purified DNDs[45,58] originating from isolated $\text{sp}^2\text{-C}$ defects as similarly observed for monocrystals after lattice damage caused by irradiation by Orwa et al.[59] Thus, irradiation produced highly defective TD_HPHT NDs showing very similar spectral features as DNDs. Hydrogenation of the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr sample led to certain healing of the diamond lattice as manifested in Raman spectra of the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H by the decrease of the $250 - 650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ feature as well as by the blue shift of the diamond peak to 1329 cm^{-1} . An amorphous sp^2C phase was also formed, as suggested by the appearance of the 1450 cm^{-1} broad band. The dark yellow spectrum of the hydrogenated TD_HPHT ND 50 without irradiation is shown as a reference and documents much better crystal quality compared to TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H sample. Thus, two hydrogenated TD_HPHT ND samples with different crystal quality were successfully prepared and further used to evaluate the impact of the structural defects on the electronic and colloidal properties.

Figure 5. Raman spectra of TD_HPHT ND 50-ar (red), the TD_HPHT ND 50-ox sample after irradiation (TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr; dark blue), TD_HPHT ND 50-ox-irr after hydrogenation (TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H; green) and referential hydrogenated TD_HPHT ND 50 (dark yellow), (a). FTIR spectra (b) of the TD_HPHT ND 50 (dark yellow) and TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H (green) samples, the conductivity values are indicated for each sample in the graph. Zeta potential and Z-average size as a function of pH for the TD_HPHT ND 50 (c) and TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H (d) samples together with photographs of the colloidal samples at a given pH one week after the measurement. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

A comparison of the FTIR spectra of the two TD_HPHT ND 50 and TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H samples in **Figure 5b** shows a striking difference in the region of the phonon frequency of the diamond ($\approx 1330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The full-range FTIR spectra are shown in Figure S3. While the transmission feature at 1330 cm^{-1} is still apparent in the TD_HPHT ND 50 sample, the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H sample exhibits a weak peak at the phonon frequency of diamond somewhat similar to DND. It must be noted here, that in DNDs the peak at 1330 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum is often associated with high nitrogen content and its intensity is typically higher. We assume that TD_HPHT ND 50 contains only 100-200 ppm of nitrogen[13], so the peak is not so pronounced. We have indicated above that the IR transmission window at 1330 cm^{-1} implicates electrical conductivity. This is further confirmed by the higher conductivity of the non-irradiated TD_HPHT ND 50 ($\approx 10^{-6} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$) than the irradiated TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H ($\approx 10^{-10} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$) sample. The introduction of the defects thus results in four orders of magnitude conductivity decrease, in fact, to the value very similar to that of DND. This clearly shows the correlation between the microstructure and conductivity and confirms that the crystal quality is the

critical parameter in controlling the electronic properties, particularly the conductivity of hydrogenated (otherwise nominally undoped) ND.

The colloidal properties of the TD_HPHT ND 50 and TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H samples were measured in the same way as in Figure 4 and are shown in Figures 5(c) and 5(d), respectively. TD_HPHT ND 50 shows a gradual increase of the Z-average size with the increasing pH and certain aggregation occurs immediately after the first pH increase above 7. The pH increase is accompanied by a continuous zeta potential decrease, reaching even negative values at a pH higher than 10. This behavior is similar to the TD_HPHT ND 18 sample (Fig. 4b), yet the zeta potential decay as function of pH is steeper which may indicate less robust colloidal properties for the larger TD_HPHT NDs. In contrast, the zeta potential of the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H exhibits a plateau at around 20 mV in the pH range of 7-11. In this pH range, the samples remain at least partially colloidally stable even after one week as demonstrated by the photographs of the colloidal samples at a given pH. Again, this behavior is similar to defective DND, including appearance of the distinct IR feature at 1570 cm^{-1} (see Figure S3) assigned to the presence of the strongly confined surface water as already discussed above. These results confirm that introducing the defects can improve the colloidal stability of hydrogenated ND at the expense of electrical conductivity deterioration.

Explanation of the highly positive zeta potential of DND despite the apparent aggregation at $\text{pH} > 9 - 10$ (Figure 4a) is not straightforward and needs further clarification. Hydrogenated DND is known for its strongly positive zeta potential and, similarly to previous study[25], IEP was not reached even at the $\text{pH} = 11-12$. Nevertheless, several points and hypotheses can be considered to shed light on this anomalous behavior. The electrophoretic mobility and the corresponding zeta potential provide an average value of the zeta potential for particles in the system[60]. However, DND exhibits an inhomogeneity of the surface charge density and degree of the particle shape/faceting related to the DND size[61]. It has been suggested recently that DND interparticle interactions result in size-dependent self-assembly, with the largest nanoparticles providing a clustered scaffold through facet-facet interactions, dominated by the $\{111\}$ surface, for subsequent smaller nanoparticle assembly. In other words, larger, faceted nanoparticles tend to pack together first, and finally, the smallest nanoparticles lose their mobility[62]. Considering these theoretical findings, the obtained results could be explained as follows: upon pH increase and related increase of the surface charge screening, the larger, faceted particles aggregate first, thus decreasing their electrophoretic mobility/zeta potential. In contrast, a fraction of smaller particles remains possibly non-aggregated even in the pH range 10-12 and may provide the recorded relatively high electrophoretic mobility and corresponding zeta potential values. In addition, the character of the DND aggregates may be rather loose, possibly enabling a certain electrokinetic motion of the particles within the aggregates, especially of the rope or chain type[63,64]. These assumptions have experimental support in the recent cryo-TEM and small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments showing the formation of loose lacey-like aggregates of primary DND particles[65]. This behavior is specific to DND with a very small size of the DND primary particles (few nm) with various shapes and degrees of faceting[52]. In contrast, both BU_HPHT ND 8 nm and TD_HPHT ND 18 nm would form tightly bound aggregates due their predominantly well-faceted character. This hypothesis cannot be, however, fully applied on the TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H sample showing a similar behavior to DND (a zeta potential “plateau” in the pH range 7-11; Fig 5d) but containing predominantly well-faceted and significantly larger particles (0-100 nm) than DND. Therefore, we also assume the involvement of surface charge accumulation enabled by surface defects and the hydrogen termination which is manifested by the distinct IR feature at 1570 cm^{-1} (see Fig. S3) and poor electrical conductivity (Fig. 2a and Fig. 5b) which is common for DND and TD_HPHT ND 50-ar-irr-H samples. Further investigation is needed to fully elucidate this anomalous colloidal behavior.

Having all the clues, let us now discuss, where the electrical conductivity of ND may arise from. First, nitrogen content could be assumed as the nitrogen is well known to generate “hopping” electrical conductivity of ultrananocrystalline diamond thin films[66] even at room temperature and as deep donor also in bulk diamond[67]. However, its content in a typical HPHT ND is too low to create such a conductivity. Moreover, nitrogen would provide the highest conductivity to DNDs and the lowest for both BU_HPHT NDs and TD_HPHT NDs, whereas the opposite is true. The nitrogen induced conductivity would also not be sensitive to surface water. The surface water is another factor to consider as it could provide some conductive network for ions. However, FTIR spectra show the least water content on the most conductive BU_HPHT NDs and TD_HPHT NDs. While the kinetics of water desorption and adsorption and strength of the hydration are different in each type of NDs (as shown also in Fig. 2(b)) it could hardly be responsible for 5 orders of magnitude difference in conductivity as observed here.

The third option is the well-known mechanism of transfer doping (reviewed recently in [1]), a process by which intrinsically insulating H-terminated diamond surfaces can become semiconducting after exposure to ambient air suggesting the presence of airborne species on the diamond surface behave as electron acceptors. This phenomenon is associated with the negative electron affinity (NEA) of the H-terminated diamond surface implying that the vacuum level at the surface lies below the conduction band minimum. The highest sensitivity of the conductivity to hydration/dehydration as observed by the FTIR and conductivity data (Figures 2 and 3) indicates that this effect is strongest in the TD_HPHT ND, less strong in DND and least strong in the BU_HPHT ND. The recent study showed that the same thermal hydrogenation method provides the TD_HPHT ND with the NEA but the electron affinity of hydrogenated DND remains positive[41]. This clearly explains the observed difference in the conductivity between the DND and TD_HPHT ND as it confirms that the transfer doping effect may occur in TD_HPHT ND in the same manner as in the hydrogenated bulk diamond surface. Interestingly, the study[41] also showed that the TD_HPHT ND-H contains the continuum of the electronic states inside the bandgap that, in addition to the transfer doping mechanism, can also contribute to electrical conductivity. Here, the conjugated sp^2 phase, i.e., the trans-polyacetylene indicated by Raman spectroscopy, most probably introduces the intra-bandgap states. This conductivity mechanism seems dominant in the BU_HPHT ND sample that showed the least sensitivity to hydration/dehydration. This assumption is further supported by the 1330 cm^{-1} conductivity-related absorption feature, which fully recovers even after the annealing at 380°C in the dry nitrogen[40]. Such “high” temperature annealing in dry nitrogen rules out the dominant contribution of the transfer doping in the BU_HPHT ND, as evidenced by the complete survival of the hydrogen termination. In addition, the clear and sharp spectral (Raman and IR) features of C-H_x bending modes[18,38,49] indicate a well-ordered and possibly conjugated structure occurring on the surface of BU_HPHT ND. The 1150 cm^{-1} and 1450 cm^{-1} features are also found in the TD_HPHT ND[28,29] but they were not reported on DNDs[41], highlighting the different surface structures of the employed three ND types.

Based on the findings above we propose a simplified model shown in the **Figure 6** that schematically visualizes relations between the structure and electronic and colloidal properties and the properties of the studied hydrogenated NDs. Firstly, DNDs can be understood as poorly conducting NDs due to the defective structure of the core and the surface. Here, the defective surface provides localized energetic states where the electrons could be trapped. The surface hydrogen termination induces electron density redistribution within a DND particle due to a small dipole of the C-H bond. The electron density redistribution could also be supported by the electron shuttling from the underlying diamond core to the surface sp^2 -C structure resulting in a denser electron population on the outer shell[68]. The high charge density localized on the DND “non-diamond” surface[37], here denoted as

amorphous C:H (a-C:H) then results in a high affinity to water and provides the DNDs a high degree of protonability, resulting in a highly positive zeta potential up to high pH values as suggested earlier[36].

TD_HPHT ND already has a significantly lower affinity to water and worse colloidal properties than DND due to lower surface charge density compared to DND. This is undoubtedly given by their monocrystalline structure and lower amount of non-diamond carbon/structural defects in the surface or sub-surface layer. For achieving stable colloidal solutions slightly acidic conditions are beneficial. The higher density of surface defects can be achieved by higher annealing temperature in hydrogen[27,29]. Similarly, irradiation of NDs resulted in the formation of bulk/surface defects. Both these treatments can be used to desirably adjust electronic and colloidal properties of TD_HPHT ND.

The BU_HPHT ND has the best quality in terms of the lowest content of non-diamond carbon/defect density but the worst colloidal properties. For the BU_HPHT ND of size above 2-3 nm, the electrical conductivity is comparable to the TD_HPHT ND. Dominant contribution, however, does not originate from the transfer doping mechanism, but it is rather provided by a conjugated surface structure.

Figure 6. Simplified scheme showing relations between the hydrogenated ND structure represented by three different types of NDs and colloidal and electronic properties. The light bulb and droplet symbols and their size represent variation of electronic and colloidal/hydration properties in dependence on the specific properties of the three ND types. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

Conclusion

We have employed three types of NDs with different sizes and structures and determined the important material properties that govern hydrogenated NDs' colloidal properties and electrical conductivity. We showed that the strongest hydration, highest zeta potential at pH 5-6, and best

colloidal stability up to basic pH are provided by the defective DND. We ascribe these characteristics to a high charge density localized on the DND “non-diamond” surface, which enables a high level of protonation. Both TD_HPHT ND 18 nm and BU_HPHT ND 8 nm exhibited lower zeta potential values at pH 5-6, weaker hydration and lower colloidal stability in basic pH. Introduction of structural defects by neutron irradiation of TD_HPHT ND increased their colloidal stability, thereby showing that the defects control colloidal properties of hydrogenated NDs.

The electrical conductivity of the samples was also measured as a function of size, structure, and ND type. We found significant differences in the conductivity of the studied samples. The conductivity of DND was low ($\approx 10^{-10}$ S.cm⁻¹) due to their defective structure. In the BU_HPHT ND we found a strong dependence on ND size and identified a threshold between insulating ($>10^{-10}$ S.cm⁻¹) and conducting samples ($< 10^{-6}$ S.cm⁻¹) located between 2-3 nm. This is probably connected with an evolution in the BU_HPHT ND shape and needs further study. The conductivity of > 4 nm BU_HPHT ND and the TD HPHT ND up to 100 nm achieved only one order magnitude lower value ($\approx 10^{-5}$ S.cm⁻¹) than hydrogenated bulk diamond monocrystal. Despite similar conductivity values of > 4 nm BU_HPHT ND and the TD HPHT ND up to 100 nm we found that transfer doping is dominant in TD_HPHT ND 18 nm whereas another process related to a conjugated surface structure dominates in the BU_HPHT ND. Four orders of magnitude decrease in the electrical conductivity in the TD_HPHT ND 50 nm sample after neutron irradiation clearly demonstrated importance of high crystal quality to achieve good electrical conductivity. We proved that the 1330 cm⁻¹ IR absorption feature is directly linked with the ND conductivity and enables to judge the ND electronic properties spectroscopically.

To sum up, different types of hydrogenated ND thus exhibit pronounced differences in the colloidal and electronic properties that are clearly linked to ND size, crystal quality, surface composition and structure.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (GACR) (Grant No. 23-04876S) and RFBR and GACR, project numbers 20-52-26017, 21-12567J. This publication was also supported by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. We also acknowledge using the CzechNanoLab research infrastructure (project No. LM2023051) and NanoEnvicZ research infrastructure (project No. LM2023066) supported by the MEYS. J. Libertinova is gratefully acknowledged for sample processing, preparation, and colloidal characterization.

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Graphical abstract:

